

Table 2. Patients characteristics.

Pts characteristics	Pts with archival samples [n = 20]	Pts with freshly collected samples [n = 20]
Age-median [IQR]	41.2 [36.8-55.8]	58 [50.3-67.8]
Histologic subtype		
NST	17	14
ILC	3	6
Grade 1	2	1
Grade 2	15	14
Grade 3	3	5
Biologic subtype		
LUM A	2	6
LUM B HER2-	18	14
Clinical stage		
IIA/B	7	0
IIIA/B/C	10	0
IV	3	20
PET SUVmax–median [IQR]	7.0 [3.8-10.6]	8.1 [4.5-13.2]

Abbreviations: pts – patients; IQR – interquartile range; NST – invasive cancer of no special type; ILC – invasive lobular cancer; LUM – luminal; PET – positron emission tomography; SUVmax – maximum standardized uptake value